

Cultivating CRIS for RDM

Technical Foundations for Sustainable Research Information Management at NFDI4Culture

Linnaea Söhn¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5101-5275>,
Tabea Tietz^{2,3} <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4950-0941>, Etienne
Posthumus² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8501-6700>, Heike
Fliegl² <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7069-9804>, and Torsten
Schrade¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0953-2818>

¹ Academy of Sciences and Literature Mainz, Germany

² FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure, Germany

³ KIT – Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany

*Correspondence: Linnaea Söhn, linnaea.soehn@adwmainz.de

Abstract

At NFDI4Culture, research data provides the fertile humus [1] from which our overarching vision grows: *Shared Data, Shared Practice, Shared Knowledge*. Our research data management, therefore, goes beyond enabling the discovery of data related to tangible and intangible cultural heritage: we actively support researchers in managing their data by making relevant resources, such as guidelines, software, and data portals, more findable for the communities under our umbrella. To this end, the consortium develops a Current Research Information System (CRIS) to collect structured metadata [2] and provide them to European infrastructures, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).¹ This effort relies on active community engagement, strong consortial collaboration, and sustainable, long-term software solutions.

At this year's CoRDI, we aim to present three of its core components:

1. The **Culture Information Portal**,² serving as a central access point to all consortial resources and integrating consortial services, such as the Educational Resource Finder,³ the Registry for Research Tools and Data Services,⁴ the Culture Knowledge Base⁵ and the Research Output Index,⁶
2. The **NFDI4Culture Metadata API**,⁷ making the portal's research information metadata available as Linked Open Data (LOD) based on the **NFDIcore Ontology**;⁸

¹ <https://eosc.eu/>

² <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E2379>

³ <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E4696>

⁴ <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E2392>

⁵ <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E3735>

⁶ <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E5082>

⁷ <https://nfdi4culture.de/id>

⁸ Cf. resources

3. The **Culture Knowledge Graph**,⁹ providing research information via a SPARQL endpoint for further data exploration and processing, such as a reporting pipeline via NocoDB.

The Culture Information Portal and NFDI4Culture Metadata API are built on the open-source Content Management System (CMS) TYPO3,¹⁰ widely used in the German academic landscape and maintained by an active community [3]. It supports content management for the consortium, allowing editors to contribute community-relevant information (e.g. news and events).

To ensure interoperability with European infrastructures, such as the OpenAIRE Graph¹¹ and the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub,¹² a dedicated TYPO3 extension is used based on the CERIF data model¹³ from euroCRIS.¹⁴ This **Academy Extension**¹⁵ enables the structured collection of information on e.g. persons, organisations, products (e.g. software), and publications following the OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS Managers [4,5].

Long-term access to CRIS resources is ensured through resolvable IRIs, generated via another generic **TYPO3 extension for LOD**.¹⁶ It also facilitates the provision of metadata through REST-APIs in various RDF-serialisations (e.g. RDFa, Turtle, JSON-LD) and mappings to external systems, such as Wikidata.¹⁷

To enrich the expressiveness of research information, the **NFDIcore Ontology** is used in the NFDI4Culture Metadata API allowing interoperability with other NFDI consortia [6]. As a mid-level ontology grounded in the process-oriented BFO 2020 framework [7,8], NFDIcore applies state-of-the-art ontology design principles to achieve semantic consistency and interoperability. Additionally, it contains mappings to vocabularies such as DCAT,¹⁸ schema.org,¹⁹ and the information artefact ontology [9], relevant for the description of research information.

Metadata from the NFDI4Culture Metadata API is integrated into the **Culture Knowledge Graph** via the **Culture Knowledge Graph Kitchen**²⁰ – a flexible Extract-Transform-Load (ETL) environment [10]. The graph connects metadata on research information with metadata on cultural-heritage data, enabling cross-resource querying, and serving as an additional backend for views in the portal itself and an exploration service based on Shmarql.²¹

Keywords: Current Research Information System, CERIF, Knowledge Graph, BFO2020, EOSC

⁹ <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E2391>

¹⁰ <https://typo3.org/>

¹¹ <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

¹² <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/all>

¹³ https://eurocris.org/eurocris_archive/cerifsupport.org/cerif-in-brief

¹⁴ <https://eurocris.org/>

¹⁵ Cf. resources

¹⁶ Cf. resources

¹⁷ <https://www.wikidata.org/>

¹⁸ <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat>

¹⁹ <http://schema.org>

²⁰ Cf. resources

²¹ Cf. resources

Resources

- Academy Current Research Information System. <https://github.com/digicademy/academy>. "TYPO3 Extension for creating a Current Research Information System (CRIS) based on the CERIF standard."
- TYPO3 Linked Open Data Extension. <https://github.com/digicademy/lod>. "TYPO3 Extension to provide a semantic layer with Hydra REST-API, RDF serialiser and IRI resolver."
- NFDIcore Ontology. <https://github.com/ISE-FIZKarlsruhe/nfdicore>. "Mid-level Ontology based on the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) developed to represent metadata on NFDI resources, such as persons, organisations and data portals."
- NFDI4Culture Ontology. <https://github.com/ISE-FIZKarlsruhe/nfdi4culture>. "Submodule of the NFDIcore Ontology designed for the special needs of metadata on research data about tangible and intangible cultural heritage."
- Knowledge Graph Kitchen. <https://gitlab.rlp.net/adwmainz/nfdi4culture/knowledge-graph/culture-kg-kitchen>. "Versatile Extract-Transform-Load (ETL) environment to consume, process and integrate data into a knowledge graph with an analyse dashboard."
- Hydra Scraper. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8409758>. "Command line tool for the comprehensive scraping of paginated APIs, RDF, file dumps, and BEACON files used by the Knowledge Graph Kitchen."
- Shmarql. <https://github.com/epoz/shmarql>. "Linked Data publishing platform to explore SPARQL endpoints."

Author contributions

Contributor	CreDIT role
Linnaea Söhn	Writing - original draft, Software, Data curation
Jonatan Jalle Steller	Writing - original draft, Software
Tabea Tietz	Writing - original draft, Resources
Alexandra Büttner	Writing - original draft, Data curation
Etienne Posthumus	Software
Oleksandra Bruns	Resources
Heike Fliegl	Project administration
Harald Sack	Supervision, Resources
Torsten Schrade	Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Software

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors gratefully acknowledge NFDI funding by DFG, project NFDI4Culture (no. 441958017).

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank all contributors to and developers of the Research Information System, the NFDIcore Ontology and the Culture Knowledge Graph. To name just a few in random order: Anastasia Wawilow, Sven Peter, Sarah Pittroff, Gabi Pahnke, Katharina Bergmann, Andrea Polywka, Melanie Größ, Martin Albrecht-Hohmaier, Sabrina Herzog, Sabrina Ujkašević, Zoe Schubert, Katja Sternitzke, Jörg Waitelonis, Sarah Rebecca Ondraszek and Frodo Podschwadek.

References

- [1] J. Rakers, B. Millers, J. Mohrbacher, et al. "Because Data Shall Grow (and we With it): Steps Towards a Cultural Change for Sharing Research Data", Proc Conf Res Data Infrastr, vol. 1, Sep. 2023. doi: 10.52825/cordi.v1i.278.
- [2] T. Tietz, O. Bruns, H. Fliegl, et al., "Knowledge Graph-basierte Forschungsdatenintegration in NFDI4Culture", presented at the DHd 2023 Open Humanities Open Culture. 9. Tagung des Verbands "Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum" (DHd 2023), Trier, Luxemburg, Mar. 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7715510.
- [3] Regionales Rechenzentrum Erlangen, "Webauftritte der Hochschulen in Deutschland". Regionales Rechenzentrum RRZE Statistiken. Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU). <https://statistiken.rrze.fau.de/webauftritte/hochschulen/> (2025-04-27).
- [4] J. Dvořák, A. Bollini, L. Rémy and J. Schirrwagen, "OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS Managers 1.1", Zenodo, Dec. 2018. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.2316420.
- [5] L. Söhn, T. Tietz, A. Büttner, et al., Finding interdisciplinary connections – Implementing FAIR research information in NFDI4Culture [Poster EOSC Symposium 2024]. Zenodo, 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13981015.
- [6] J. Waitelonis, O. Bruns, T. Tietz, E. Posthumus, H. B. Nasrabadi, and H. Sack, "Introduction". NFDIcore Ontology, revision 3.0.1, <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/docs/intro/> (2025-04-27).
- [7] B. Smith and T. B. Developers, Basic Formal Ontology (BFO), revision 2020-08-26, <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/bfo.owl> (2025-04-27).
- [8] R. Arp, B. Smith, and A. D. Spear, Building Ontologies with Basic Formal Ontology. MIT Press, 2015.
- [9] S. Arabandi, C. A. Boelling, M. Brochhausen, et al., Information artefact ontology (iao), <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/iao.owl> (2025-04-27).
- [10] O. Bruns, T. Tietz, L. Söhn, et al., What's Cooking in the NFDI4Culture Kitchen? A KG-based Research Data Integration Workflow, in Proc. of 4th Workshop on Metadata and Research (objects) Management for Linked Open Science - DaMaLOS 2024, Mai 2024. doi: 10.4126/FRL01-006474028.